

CALCULATION OF THE VOLUME OF A CIRCULAR BODY

Djumabayev G'ulomjon Xalillayevich

T.f.d.d dotsent CHDPU MO'M

Department of geometry, Docent

Abdullayeva Shahlo Abduqodir qizi

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Master

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10958410>

Keywords: calculations, mathematical theories, circular body, cones, three-dimensional shape

Introduction: Thus, you will find that the method of using calculus to find volumes is far superior and has many more applications than the traditional geometry methods. With this in mind, we should understand the nature of variables and equations in terms of a 3D area. At this point, the important question to ask is: What is the volume of a volume? Step one is defining a volume, and this can be done simply using a triple integral, which is a standard method of finding 3D entities, and the result is a numerical value.

A much simpler method, which can be used for regular and irregular shapes, involves using integral calculus to find the volume. Now, why would you want to use calculus to solve such a problem when there are many geometry rules designed specifically for finding areas and volumes? Well, we know the difficulty in finding the area under a curve, and in many cases, most irregular shapes can be considered as a series of curves which are 2D. So, we already have the tools required to find the volume of a 3D shape! Calculus methods can also be applied to volumes of revolution, which is a topic covered in Engineering Mathematics (e.g., using steel to shape a bridge or car part).

Volume may be defined as the quantity of three-dimensional space enclosed by some closed boundary or the space a substance occupies. Volume can be determined by fluid displacement, constructing a model with water, or using less reliable methods using the geometry of the area in question.

The purpose of the calculation is to determine the volume of a shape that represents human lung airways, i.e. a 3- or 2-dimensional pathway. To do this, we will take a phantom of lung airways and calculate its volume. This means some assumptions are made to convert this phantom of airways into a solid shape. By doing this, it provides a real quantity for comparison with other measures. This has been done using widely varying techniques for different studies (e.g. water displacement, Cine CT Scanning). By calculating the volume of our shape, we are providing a modern quantitative analysis of airway

abnormalities. This is crucial for the detection of diseases such as asthma, which constrict the airways, decreasing airflow to the lungs. The principle becomes more difficult when the shape of the object to be calculated is irregular, making the application of a formula impossible. One method of calculating the volume of an irregular object is to submerge it in a liquid of known density and measure the force on the object by the liquid, as the weight of the liquid displaced will be equal to the weight of the object. The volume can then be calculated by knowing the density of the liquid and the force acting on the object. This method is, however, not always possible or practical, and the usual process would be to extract or approximate the irregular object to a series of known shapes for which formulae exist, determine the volumes of the known shapes, and apply addition or subtraction to find a total volume. An easier method, however, would be to use calculus, more specifically integration, to determine an exact mathematical volume.

In essence, the volume of an object is, by its simplest definition, the amount of 3-dimensional space the object occupies. The determination of volume is a significant application in many areas of everyday life and can be as simple as determining how much water to fill a bucket or how much sand and cement is required to fill a hole in the ground. The principle of determining the volume of an object can be a simple process if the object has a regular shape for which a mathematical formula is provided. The appropriate formula can be applied, and the calculation performed quite easily. Take, for example, a brick – it is a regular cuboid shape and has a volume $V = lwh$.

The calculation of the volume of a circular body is a fundamental concept in mathematics and geometry. Understanding how to calculate the volume of a circular body is essential for various fields such as engineering, architecture, and physics.

To begin with, let us define what a circular body is. A circular body is a three-dimensional shape that is formed by rotating a two-dimensional circle around an axis. Examples of circular bodies include cylinders, cones, and spheres. These shapes have circular bases and curved surfaces that are characteristic of circular bodies.

The volume of a circular body can be calculated using different formulas depending on the shape of the body. For a cylinder, the formula for calculating the volume is $V = \pi r^2 h$, where V is the volume, r is the radius of the base of the cylinder, and h is the height of the cylinder. This formula is derived from the fact

that the volume of a cylinder is equal to the area of the base (πr^2) multiplied by the height.

For a cone, the formula for calculating the volume is $V = (1/3) \pi r^2 h$, where V is the volume, r is the radius of the base of the cone, and h is the height of the cone. This formula is derived from the fact that the volume of a cone is equal to one-third of the volume of a cylinder with the same base and height.

Lastly, for a sphere, the formula for calculating the volume is $V = (4/3) \pi r^3$, where V is the volume and r is the radius of the sphere. This formula is derived from the fact that the volume of a sphere is equal to four-thirds of the volume of a circumscribing cylinder with the same radius. In order to calculate the volume of a circular body, it is important to know the dimensions of the body such as the radius and height. By plugging these values into the appropriate formula, one can easily determine the volume of the circular body.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the calculation of the volume of a circular body is a crucial concept in mathematics and geometry. By understanding the formulas and methods used to calculate the volume of different circular bodies, one can apply this knowledge to various real-world applications. Whether it be designing a building, constructing a bridge, or analyzing the behavior of a physical system, the ability to calculate the volume of a circular body is a valuable skill that is essential for success in many fields.

References:

1. S. Brambilla et al. Adhesion and aerodynamic forces for the resuspension of non-spherical particles in outdoor environments *Journal of Aerosol Science* (2017)
2. E. Ermis et al. Centrifugal tester versus a novel design to measure particle adhesion strength and investigation of effect of physical characteristics (size, shape, density) of food particles on food surfaces *J Food Eng* (2011)
3. G. Xiao et al. A PZT-assisted single particle loading method for dual-fiber optical trap in air *Optics & Laser Technology* (2020)
4. Z. Fu et al. Launch and capture of a single particle in a pulse-laser-assisted dual-beam fiber-optic trap *Opt Commun* (2018)
5. H.W. Zhang et al. Parametric variational principle and quadratic programming method for van der Waals force simulation of parallel and cross nanotubes *Int J. Solids Structures* (2007)
6. H.C. Hamaker: The London—Van der Waals attraction between spherical particles *Physica* (1937)

7. B.V. Derjaguin et al. Effect of contact deformations on the adhesion of particles J Colloid Interface (1975)